
Research

Hybrid CNN-RNN and SVM Techniques for Improved Webshell Detection

Mst Habiba Farhana*, Ridoy Kumar Roy

School of Computer Science & Software Engineering, Hohai University, Nanjing, China
College of Information Science & Engineering, Hohai University, Nanjing, China

Abstract: The rapid growth of the internet has significantly changed lives and business processes, enabling unprecedented connectivity and creativity. However, this digital progress has raised the risks of cybercrime, needing strong security measures for web servers. Among the different cyber threats webshell attacks pose a significant risk by exploiting system vulnerabilities and undermine system integrity. While traditional detection techniques, such as rule-based heuristics and signature-based approaches, were once effective, they now struggle to keep up with attackers advanced attacks strategies. These static approaches, which rely on predetermined patterns or signatures, are ineffective at detecting obscured, polymorphic, or innovative attack variants, leaving systems vulnerable to undiscovered breaches. This study presents a unique machine learning based technique to webshell identification that combines Support Vector Machines (SVM) with Convolutional Neural Networks and Recurrent Neural Networks (CNN-RNN). By studying the diversity of webshells and resolving the constraints of existing detection approaches, the proposed ensemble method significantly improves detection accuracy. Additionally, a user-friendly Graphical User Interface (GUI) was developed to facilitate model selection, data entry, and performance monitoring, providing system administrators and cyber security professionals with an accessible and effective tool for enhancing web server security.

Keywords: Webshell, Machine Learning, Deep Neural Network, SVM, CNN-RNN, ADFa-LD.

*Corresponding Author: farhanashova32@gmail.com

Accepted: 28 November, 2024; **Published:** 29 November, 2024

How to cite this article: Mst Habiba Farhana, Ridoy Kumar Roy (2024). Hybrid CNN-RNN and SVM Techniques for Improved Webshell Detection. *North American Academic Research*, 7(12), 71-90. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14515947>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2024 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

With over 4.5 billion users and more than 8 billion connected mobile devices, has heightened the vulnerability of the global network to cyber-attacks. Webshells—malicious scripts that exploit vulnerabilities in servers or applications are among the most significant threats to information security. These scripts are widely used during the post-exploitation phase of cyber-attacks, enabling attackers to maintain access, facilitate data breaches, and execute other malicious actions. Effective global network security hinges on the accurate detection of webshell attacks. Traditional intrusion detection systems (IDS), such as anomaly-based (AIDS) and signature-based (SIDS) methods, fail to effectively detect sophisticated attacks, such as zero-day vulnerabilities. To overcome these limitations, machine learning and deep learning algorithms have emerged as promising solutions for webshell detection, enabling improved detection accuracy

and resilience to emerging threats. Datasets such as ADFA-LD, which contain system call traces for both normal and malicious activity, are essential for developing and evaluating these advanced detection approaches.

The ongoing evolution of webshell detection emphasizes the urgent need for improved methods to counter increasingly complex cyber-attacks and safeguard the integrity of digital infrastructure.

Related works

The Webshells are a major security threat, allowing attackers remote access and control of web servers [1]. Many webshell detection techniques based on machine learning and deep learning have been proposed by researchers in recent years. A pioneering machine learning method for identifying webshells was introduced by Mohammad at 2014[2]. They employed a Naive Bayes classifier to identify webshells by analyzing their code characteristics. The method under consideration achieved an accuracy rate of 96.5%. In the context of webshell detection, [3] proposed an SVM-based approach that extracts features from the source code of web pages and uses them as input to the SVM algorithm for effective detection. The experimental results showed that their approach achieved a high accuracy rate in detecting webshells. Other ML methods for classification tasks include K-nearest neighbors (KNN), logistic regression, and naive Bayes. KNN is a simple ML method that classifies a data point based on the majority class of its k-nearest neighbors [4]. According to its capacity to automatically extract intricate patterns and features from massive datasets, deep learning-based host-based webshell detection has drawn a lot of attention. A deep belief network (DBN) model for webshell identification was introduced by Yuan et al. (2016), one of the first publications on this subject [5]. A hybrid deep learning model for webshell identification that incorporates long short-term memory (LSTM) networks and convolutional neural networks (CNN) was presented by Li et al. (2021) [6].

The study "Webshell Detection Based on Deep Learning" by Li et al. (2023) presents a deep learning model dubbed Deep WebShell they extracted attributes from webshell code and classified it as benign or malicious using a combination of long short-term memory (LSTM) networks and convolutional neural networks (CNNs). In Wang et al.'s publication, the authors were able to identify Webshells written in PHP, JSP, ASPX, and ASP. PHP-type, JSP-type, and ASP-type webshells using "A New Method for WebShell Detection Based on Bidirectional GRU and Attention Mechanism" (2023) [7]. Zhang et al.'s paper "WebShell Detection Based on Deep Learning with Transfer Learning" (2023) provides a deep learning and transfer learning approach for webshell detection. He extracted features from webshell code using a pre-trained deep learning model, then adjusted the model for webshell identification using ADFA-LD dataset. [8].

Webshell

The basic concept behind a webshell is to give an attacker an easy way to use a compromised web server to perform additional attacks. Sending HTTP queries to a certain page and utilizing certain features. Webshell can carry out the attacker's instructions. The attacker will receive the output of these instructions as a response to these HTTP requests [6].

A. Classification and Types of Webshell

Depending on the purposes of the attacker, the target system, and the techniques and instruments at their disposal, different kinds of webshells can be used. Here we discuss the common types of webshells-

- **Simple Webshells:** Basic webshells allow attackers to execute commands, modify files, and escalate privileges. They are easier to detect due to simple functions like "popen" or "shell_exec".
- **Complex Webshells:** Feature-rich with GUIs, enabling file manipulation, database access, network communication, and more. Examples include WSO, c99, B347K, and r57.

- **Bind Shell:** Monitors a device for incoming connections, allowing remote program execution.
- **Reverse Shell:** Creates a connection from the target to the attacker's machine, useful for remote manipulation despite NAT or firewall restrictions.
- **Double Reverse Shell:** Similar to reverse shell, but with two ports for bidirectional communication.
- **Basic Command Execution Webshells:** Simple shells for executing standard commands like "ls" or "pwd".
- **File Manager Webshells:** Provides a graphical interface for file management, including uploading, downloading, renaming, and deleting files.
- **Backdoor Webshells:** Offers concealed access to web servers, persisting even after initial compromise.

Webshells are developed in various languages, with PHP being common, but others like ASP, Python, Perl, Ruby, and Unix are also used. Their choice depends on attacker objectives, target systems, and available tools.

B. How Webshell Works and Used by Attackers

Webshells capitalize on command injection flaws by executing other processes using programming language methods such as *system()* and *exec()*. If attackers can access the arguments given to these functions, they can execute instructions on the target host. A PHP-capable website, for example, with a vulnerable script, may enable attackers to send malicious queries. Webshells provide attackers with a wide range of capabilities, from basic command-line interactions to advanced database or file browser interfaces, allowing mission for efficient exploitation and data manipulation. The figure below illustrates a webshell attacks cycle.

Figure: Webshell Attacks Scheme

Webshells allow attackers to bypass file validation, often by changing the 'Content-Type' header, allowing malicious scripts to be uploaded and run remotely on compromised servers. For instance, attackers can use specially constructed URLs to get access to sensitive files or run commands. Webshells are also used to operate botnets for DDoS attacks, serving as command-and-control centers to disguise activity and avoid discovery.

These technologies enable attackers to execute a variety of operations, including initiating processes, executing commands, and connecting with other networked systems. They maintain persistence by altering server settings, allowing for continued access. Furthermore, webshells allow for lateral movement within networks, expanding the attacker's reach and enabling additional exploitation.

Host Based Webshell Detection

HIDS, or Host-based Intrusion Detection Systems, are programs that monitor individual host systems, such as servers, laptops, mobile devices, and other endpoints, for suspicious activity. These activities could involve both external intrusions and internal exploitation of resources or data.

The primary function of a HIDS is to detect suspicious activity or strange patterns that could signal a system compromise. When a HIDS detects such activity, it flags it for analysis, allowing the security team to assess the threat and take appropriate action before any damage takes place [9]. HIDS often detects malicious behavior by analyzing sequences of system events such as bash commands or system calls. System calls are the interface through which user-space programs can request services from the operating system's kernel, such as creating a new process or reading a file. HIDS scans incoming and outgoing network packets and notifies the user if any dangers are discovered (Figure below). They are placed at the endpoint to monitor network traffic to and from the machine.

Figure: Workflow of Host-based IDS

To discriminate between malicious and benign behavior, HIDS use machine learning and Deep Learning to evaluate system call sequences. They collect host-specific data, such as system calls, DLL files, system logs, and configuration keys [10], and use signature or anomaly based detection algorithms to detect unusual process activity.

Machine Learning

Webshell detection has emerged as a key cyber security concern as online-based attacks to get more sophisticated and the volume of web traffic increases. Webshells pose serious threats to online applications and servers, demanding the development of effective detection methods. System calls, the interface between applications and the operating system, give precise information about a process's activities. Monitoring these calls can show patterns suggestive of webshell activity, such as increases in read or write operations, allowing for the detection of malicious behaviors.

Machine Learning (ML) has developed as an efficient method for detecting webshells, providing analytical models that learn from system activity and identify anomalies without human intervention. ML approaches may be divided into three types: supervised learning, which employs labeled datasets; unsupervised learning, which finds patterns in unlabeled data, which optimizes behaviors via trial and error. Linear Regression, Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, SVMs, Naïve Bayes, and KNN are popular machine learning algorithms that accurately find complicated patterns in huge datasets. ML's versatility, scalability, and capacity to handle large amounts of traffic make it ideal for real-time webshell detection.

Deep Learning (DL), a subset of ML, improves webshell identification by using neural networks to examine data without explicit feature construction. CNNs and RNNs are examples of deep learning models that automatically extract characteristics from sources such as server logs and system events, minimizing manual effort and increasing detection accuracy. These models can recognize both known and undiscovered webshell threats. Despite constraints such as high processing needs and interpretability concerns, deep learning provides substantial benefits, including better accuracy, flexibility, and scalability. Its ability to identify zero-day attacks emphasizes its potential for improving cyber security.

Methodology

This research proposes a Python-based application that uses machine learning and deep learning approaches to identify system call sequences as legitimate or malicious. The program uses two models: Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and a hybrid Convolutional Neural Network-Recurrent Neural Network (CNN-RNN). The SVM model, a supervised learning strategy, classifies data in an N-dimensional space by determining the best hyper plane that maximizes class separation. For this work, SVM manages the dataset's non-linear connections using kernel functions such as radial basis function (RBF), linear, and polynomial, guaranteeing appropriate categorization of system calls as normal or attack behaviors.

Figure: SVM Architecture

Linear SVM is a support vector machine (SVM) that classifies data points using a linear kernel. In other words, it determines the ideal hyper plane that separates the two classes by the greatest margin. The linear kernel function is expressed as:

$$K(x, y) = x^T y \tag{1}$$

The *SVM Model* class defines the SVM model. The model employs a radial basis function (RBF) kernel; however, alternative kernels, such as "linear" and "poly," are also accessible. The *SVC* class from the *sklearn.svm* module, which defaults to a linear kernel, is used with two data points (x, y). The mathematical formula for linear support vector machines is:

$$minimize = \frac{1}{2} ||w||^2 \tag{2}$$

Subject to the constraints:

$$y_i (w \cdot x_i + b) \geq 1$$

Where $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$ {N for training sample}

where w is the weight vector, b is the bias term, and x_i and y_i are the input features and labels, respectively.

Table: SVM Model Architecture

SVM Model Architecture Definition	
Hyper parameter	C 1.0 Kernel linear gamma 1
Data Split	Testing 40% Training 60%

The following hyper parameters are employed for tuning the model's hyper parameters once it has been trained using GridSearchCV:

The Support Vector Machine (SVM) model in the program utilizes three key parameters to enhance its classification performance. The regularization parameter C manages the trade-off between minimizing training error and maximizing the decision margin, with a higher C imposing stricter penalties for misclassification; in this program, C=1, as shown in Figure below. The gamma parameter, which defines the width of the Gaussian radial basis function (RBF), influences the concentration of the decision boundary, with higher gamma values leading to narrower boundaries; its value is specified in the Figure above. Additionally, the kernel function determines how input data is transformed into higher-dimensional space for classification. Among the available kernel options—'linear,' 'rbf,' and 'poly'—the program uses the 'linear' kernel, as indicated in Figure below.

The SVM method determines the most optimal hyper plane that divides the data points into two classes with the greatest margin [50]. The dimension of the hyper plane utilized in the SVM model is determined by the number of features in the input data. The SVM model is determined by the FeatureExtractor.sequences_to_features() method. This method takes a list of sequences as input and produces a list of feature vectors, each with a length equal to MAX_SYS_CALL + 1. The MAX_SYS_CALL variable is set to 0 and modified during the data loading procedure to reflect the highest system call value identified in the dataset. The decision function:

$$F(x) = w^T x + b \tag{3}$$

```

Train the SVM model.
***
try:
    param_grid = {
        'C': [0.1, 1, 10, 100],
        'gamma': [1, 0.1, 0.01, 0.001],
        'kernel': ['linear', 'rbf', 'poly']
    }
    svm_classifier = SVC(random_state=42)
    grid_search = GridSearchCV(estimator=svm_classifier, param_grid=param_grid, cv=2, verbose=2)
    start_time = time.time() # Record start time
    grid_search.fit(train_features, trainY)

    # Log best parameters to GUI output log window
    logging.info("SVM Model Hyperparameters:")
    logging.info("Best Parameters: %s", grid_search.best_params_)
    logging.info("Best Estimator: %s", grid_search.best_estimator_)

    svm_classifier = SVC(C=1.0, kernel='linear', gamma=1, random_state=42)
    svm_classifier.fit(train_features, trainY)

    joblib.dump(svm_classifier, "svm_model.joblib")

return svm_classifier, start_time
except Exception as e:
    logging.error("Error occurred during SVM model training: %s", e)
    raise e
    
```

Figure: SVM Model structure

The function defines a hyperplane where w is a weight vector of length MAX_SYS_CALL, x is an input feature vector of length MAX_SYS_CALL + 1, and b is the bias term. The decision function computes the dot product of w and x, then adds b. The classification is determined by the sign of the decision function's output.

The distance between a data point (x_i) and the decision border can be determined as follows:

$$d_i = \frac{w^T x_i + b}{||w||} \tag{4}$$

where ||w|| denotes the Euclidean norm of the weight vector w. Euclidean norm of the normal vector W.

The SVC class from the sklearn.svm package, which employs the soft margin SVM algorithm by default. The C parameter is set to 1.0 by default, however it can be changed by the user to balance margin maximization with classification error.

Convolutional - Recurrent Neural Network (CNN-RNN)

Deep Learning, often known as Deep Neural Network, refers to multi-layered Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is one of the most often used deep neural networks. It derives its name from the

mathematical linear action between matrices known as convolution. It is commonly used for deep learning on picture datasets. CNN, like Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), has three layers: input, hidden layer(s), and output. CNNs include several layers, including a convolutional layer, a nonlinearity layer, a pooling layer, and a fully connected layer.

Figure: Basic structure of 1D CNN

Humans identify images by combining all of the many local elements that they scan with their eyes. That's how a fresh image appears to us. This method is used by CNN to accurately classify images.

$$s[t] = (x * w)[t] = \sum_{a=-\infty}^{a=\infty} x[a]w[a + t] \tag{5}$$

The *CNNRNNModel* class implements the CNN-RNN model. The CNN-RNN model is built with the Sequential class from the tensorflow.keras.models package. The model is made up the following layers: LSTM, Dense, MaxPooling1D, Conv1D, and Embedding.

Table: Used Layers in CNN-RNN

Layer Type	Functionality	Parameters
Embedding Layer	Dense vector representation of calls	Output Dim: 128
Conv1D Layer	Feature extraction from sequences	Filters: 64, Kernel size: 3
Maxpooling1D Layer	Dimensionality reduction	Pool size: 2
LSTM Layer	Capturing long-term dependencies	Unit :100
Dense Layer	Classification output	Unit: 2 (Softmax)

Embedding Layer

The Embedding layer is responsible for converting system call input sequences into dense representations. This layer is used to map each integer in the input sequence to a dense vector of fixed size. The layer's input form is *(None, MAX_SEQUENCES_LEN)*, where *None* indicates the batch size and *MAX_SEQUENCES_LEN* denotes the maximum length of the input sequences. The layer's output form is *(None, MAX_SEQUENCES_LEN, 128)*, with **128** representing the number of dimensions in the dense representation.

Conv1D layer

This layer performs a one-dimensional convolution on the embedding layer output. In a convolutional layer, the number of parameters would be:

$$((m * n) + 1) * k \quad (6)$$

In our research the purpose of this layer is to extract features from the input data by applying a set of filters to it. This layer performs convolution operations on the input data to extract features. It has **64** filters, a kernel size of **3**, and a 'same' padding. The layer's input shape is $(None, MAX_SEQUENCES_LEN, 128)$, and its output shape is $(None, MAX_SEQUENCES_LEN, 64)$, where 64 represents the number of filters employed in the convolution operation.

MaxPooling1D layer

This layer performs maximum pooling along the input sequence axis. It reduces the spatial dimensions of the input data. The purpose of this layer is to reduce the dimensionality of the input data and prevent over fitting. This layer down samples the input along the spatial dimensions by taking the maximum value within a sliding window. It has a pool size of **2**. Conducts max pooling on the Conv1D layer's output. The layer's input shape is $(None, MAX_SEQUENCES_LEN, \text{and } 64)$, whereas its output shape is $(None, MAX_SEQUENCES_LEN/2)$. By using max pooling, this layer lowers the dimensionality of the data, which lowers computational costs and increases the adaptability of the features that the convolutional layers extract.

LSTM layer (RNN - Long Short-Term Memory)

The architecture of an RNN with LSTM is designed to handle sequences of data by maintaining a memory of previous inputs and managing long-term dependencies. It has **100** units. This layer provides a long short-term memory (LSTM) operation on the MaxPooling1D layer output. The layer's input shape is $(None, MAX_SEQUENCES_LEN/2, 64)$, and its output shape is $(None, 100)$, where 100 denotes the number of units in the LSTM layer. LSTM consists of "context" or "cell" state which acts like a conveyor belt which runs over the sequence of input and stores additional state values over time [10][11]. LSTM replaces traditional RNN with input gates, output gates and forget gates. Each gate provide access to the cells in such a way that values can be stored in the cell for either short or long periods of time and removed when no longer needed.

Here are the key equations that govern the LSTM network:

The Forget Gate: Decides what information from the previous cell state to discard:

$$f_t = \sigma (W_{fx} x_t + W_{fh} h_{t-1} + b_f) \quad (7)$$

The Input Gate: determines which new information to update the cell state with:

$$i_t = \sigma (W_{ix} x_t + W_{ih} h_{t-1} + b_i) \quad (8)$$

Cell Gate: The cell gate generates a candidate cell state:

$$g_t = \tanh (W_{gx} x_t + W_{gh} h_{t-1} + b_g) \quad (9)$$

Cell State Update: The cell state at time step t is updated as follows:

$$c_t = f_t \odot c_{t-1} + i_t \odot g_t \quad (10)$$

Output Gate: The output gate determines the output from the cell state:

$$o_t = \sigma (W_{ox} x_t + W_{oh} h_{t-1} + b_o) \quad (11)$$

Activation functions

Activation functions in artificial neural networks (ANNs) convert input data into outputs that are transferred to the next layer, which has a major impact on prediction accuracy [12]. This study employs two activation functions, Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) and Softmax.

ReLU, a non-linear operation, introduces non-linearity to convolutional networks, which is a necessary feature for processing real-world data. It turns all negative values to zero while keeping positive values, resulting in non-negative linear outputs in the network. Equation 3 provides a mathematical formulation of ReLU.

$$f(x) = \max(0, x) \quad (12)$$

`model.add(Conv1D(filters=64, kernel_size=3, padding='same', activation='relu'))`

The *ReLU* activation function outputs zero for negative inputs and retains positive values, introducing non-linearity to help models learn complex patterns. It is particularly effective in convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [13].

Softmax, a hybrid function, outputs values between 0 and 1, representing class probabilities, making it suitable for classification tasks.

$$\sigma(z)_j = \frac{e^{z_j}}{\sum_{k=1}^K e^{z_k}} \text{ for } j = 1, \dots, K \tag{13}$$

Here, an exponential function is applied to each element z_i of an input vector z and normalizing these values by dividing with the sum of all the exponents. The sum of the components in the output vector $\sigma(z)$.

Dense Layer

The dense layer outputs the final classification probabilities. It has 2 units and a softmax activation function. This layer applies a dense (fully connected) operation to the output of the LSTM layer.

`model.add(Dense(2, activation='softmax'))`

The layer's input shape is $(None, 100)$, and the output shape is $(None, 2)$, where 2 represents the number of classes in the classification issue.

So, the *CNNRNNModel* class implements the CNN-RNN model. The CNN-RNN model is built with the Sequential class from the tensorflow.keras.models package. The model is made up the following layers: LSTM, Dense, MaxPooling1D, Conv1D, and Embedding.

Table: CNN-RNN Model Architecture

CNN-RNN Model Architecture Definition	
Layers	Embedding layer with 128 dimensions Conv1D layer with 64 filters, kernel size 3, and padding same MaxPooling1D layer with pool size 2 LSTM layer with 100 units Dense layer with 2 units and softmax activation
Hyper parameters	Batch size: 64 Number of epochs:15
Data Split	Training: 60% Testing 40%

The figure below depicts the model's architecture, which includes key parameters and functions that have previously been discussed in depth.

```
def create_model():
    """
    Create the CNN-RNN model architecture.
    """
    try:
        model = Sequential()
        model.add(Embedding(MAX_SYS_CALL + 1, 128, input_length=MAX_SEQUENCES_LEN))
        model.add(Conv1D(filters=64, kernel_size=3, padding='same', activation='relu'))
        model.add(MaxPooling1D(pool_size=2))
        model.add(LSTM(100))
        model.add(Dense(2, activation='softmax'))
        model.compile(loss='binary_crossentropy', optimizer='adam', metrics=['accuracy'])
        return model
    except Exception as e:
        logging.error("Error occurred while creating CNN-RNN model: %s", e)
        raise e
```

Figure: CNN-RNN Model Architecture

Overall, The CNN-RNN model comprises two CNN layers: an Embedding layer and a Conv1D layer, followed by a MaxPooling1D layer to down sample spatial dimensions. An LSTM layer processes sequential data and captures long-term dependencies, while a dense layer outputs the final categorization results. The model uses the binary_crossentropy loss function, Adam optimizer, and accuracy metric which is trained with the fit method, using TensorFlow Keras for implementation and storage.

The model performs binary classification to differentiate between normal and abnormal system call sequences, evaluated using metrics like recall, F1 score, and accuracy, precision, and confusion matrices. Cross-validation, with a 60-40 dataset split for training and testing and further division into five folds, ensures generalizability and mitigates over fitting. The detailed architecture is depicted in the Figure below-

Figure: System Process Workflow Diagram

The figure above represents a system process workflow diagram. The detailed explanation is as follows:

- **Data Collection:** The ADFA-LD dataset, which includes system call traces from both attack and normal circumstances, serves as the process' basis. The dataset's logs are divided into two directories for normal and attack data, ensuring clarity and simplicity of access.
- **Data Load:** A graphical user interface (GUI) allows the user to specify the directories that hold normal and attack data. The *DataLoader* module extracts data from the specified directories. The *load_data* function is specifically responsible for loading both normal and attack data and prepares it for further processing.
- **Feature Extraction:** *FeatureExtractor* module processes the loaded data and extracts useful features. This is accomplished by the *sequences_to_features* method, which converts a sequence of each system call within the sequences to generate feature vectors.
- **Model selection:** Users can choose a model for analysis through the GUI, which includes Support Vector Machine (SVM) and CNN-RNN. The chosen model is trained and run on data from the provided directories for both normal and attack circumstances.
- **Model training and evaluation (SVM):** The *SVMModel* module is used to construct the SVM model. The *train_model* function employs GridSearchCV to identify the optimal hyperparameters, whilst the *evaluate_and_log* method evaluates the model and logs performance metrics. The *run_svm* function makes it easier to train and run the SVM model using the provided data.
- **Model Training and Evaluation (CNN-RNN):** When CNN-RNN is chosen, the *CNNRNNModel* module

conducts the operation. The *create_model* method defines the model design, whereas the *evaluate_and_log* function analyzes performance metrics. The *run_cnn_rnn* method is responsible for training and running the CNN-RNN model on the provided data.

- **Performance Metrics and the Confusion Matrix:** Accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and the confusion matrix are all recorded in a file and in the GUI's log section. Additionally, graphical charts of accuracy and validation metrics for the chosen model are created.
- **Model Detection:** *ModelDetectionGUI* module identifies webshell attacks in new system call records. Users can specify the file to be detected and use the *detect_data_by_SVM* or *detect_data_by_CNRRNN* methods to load the trained model, extract features from the input file, and predict whether it is normal or attacked.
- **Result:** The GUI displays the results of the detection (normal file or webshell).

Dataset (ADFA-LD)

In the context of Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS), datasets are used to train models to recognize normal and abnormal system calls. These datasets include the generated system call ids. The KDD dataset, commonly known as the DARPA dataset, and the UNM dataset are two widely used IDS datasets [14]. However, these datasets are deemed outdated and inefficient for modern system call analysis.

On the other hand, the ADFA dataset, which was introduced in 2013, is a more up-to-date and efficient dataset for IDS. The Australian Defense Force Academy (ADFA) developed the ADFA IDS Datasets by gathering system call traces from both legitimate and malicious Linux applications. The ADFA_LD dataset, which uses system call IDs, a labeled dataset that includes both normal and malicious system call traces. The normal traces were received from a variety of sources, including the Linux operating system, whereas the malicious traces were obtained from the Linux Malware Archive and the Contagio Malware Dump. The ADFA-LD was developed to give performance evaluation a contemporary viewpoint. A part of the system calls in Linux Kernel 2.6.38 from the ADFA-LD dataset as shown in the figure below.

Number	Name
0	sys_restart_syscall
1	sys_exit
2	sys_fork
...	...
168	sys_poll
...	...
265	sys_clock_gettime
...	...
323	sys_eventfd
324	sys_fallocate


```

#define __NR_io_setup 0 __SYSCALL(__NR_io_setup, sys_io_setup)
#define __NR_io_destroy 1 __SYSCALL(__NR_io_destroy, sys_io_destroy)
#define __NR_io_submit 2 __SYSCALL(__NR_io_submit, sys_io_submit)
#define __NR_io_cancel 3 __SYSCALL(__NR_io_cancel, sys_io_cancel)
#define __NR_io_getevents 4 __SYSCALL(__NR_io_getevents, sys_io_getevents)
#define __NR_setxattr 5 __SYSCALL(__NR_setxattr, sys_setxattr)
#define __NR_lsetxattr 6 __SYSCALL(__NR_lsetxattr, sys_lsetxattr)
    
```

Figure: A Part of System call in Linux Kernel 2.6.38

(1) Attack structure:[15][16][17][18]

Payload / Effect	Vector
Password bruteforce	FTP by Hydra
Password bruteforce	SSH by Hydra
Add new superuser	Client-Side Poisoned executable
Java Based Meterpreter	Tiki Wiki vulnerability exploit
Linux Meterpreter Payload	Client-Side poisoned executable
C100 Webshell	PHP Remote File Inclusion vulnerability

Figure: Attack Structure

The first two attack types represent systematic sequences in which an attacker attempts to brute force password

guessing on an open service. Elevating privileges in a Linux environment in this dataset, a client-side attack was used to add a new superuser payload.

The attacker uses Meterpreter which is a custom payload unique to the free Metasploit framework. To enhanced functionality command shell that greatly facilitates remote compromise of target systems they used Meterpreter.

Similarly, a Linux executable version of the Meterpreter payload was uploaded using social engineering and similar operations performed. This represents a different attack on the Java version.

Finally, a PHP-based remote file inclusion vulnerability is used to upload the C100 webshell, which was used to further compromise the host system and escalate privileges. The C100 shell is a complex PHP code that provides an attacker with an illegal GUI interface via a web browser, allowing manipulation of the underlying operating system.

(2) Dataset Structure:

The data set is divided into three groups, each group contains the original system call sequence.

Figure: Dataset Structure

The data for each training set (*Training_Data_Master*) and validation set (*Validation_Data_Master*) is collected during the normal operation of the host, including various activities from browsing the web to preparing latex documents. The call sequence is generated by the audited Unix program and then filtered by size. The training set data size is between 300 bits and 6kb, and the validation set data is between 300kb and 10kb. This is to effectively balance data fidelity and unnecessary processing burden.

There are 6 attack methods in the attack data set (*Attack_Data_Master*) explained in the figure above: Attack Structure. As we have previously mentioned that the ADFA data set has characterized system calls, so for each system call function, ADFA has been numbered with numbers. The corresponding number can be found in the Figure below File structure.

ADFA-LD+Syscall+List.txt file

Figure: File Structure

Experiment Libraries

In the implementation of this program, various machine-learning, deep learning and python libraries are deployed to support various tasks related to data preprocessing, feature extraction, model training, and evaluation. The implementation utilizes the following libraries:

Numpy [19], joblib [20], tkinter [21], Filedialog, messagebox, tensorflow, keras, Matplotlib, Scikit-learn, Time, os, functools, logging.

Graphical Interface Implementation

The graphic interface is designed using the Tkinter library in Python. Tkinter is a standard library for creating graphical user interfaces (GUIs) with widgets like buttons, labels, and entry fields. It defines three main components: Main Menu (MainGUI), Train Model(GUI), and Model Detection (ModelDetectionGUI). Each class creates a different window with its own set of widgets and functionality.

1. Main Menu(MainGUI)

The main window named "Main Menu" with dimensions of 400x300 pixels is created by the *MainGUI* class. It has two buttons on it.

Train Model: 100x30 pixels, centered. Clicking it launches the GUI class's main function and creates an instance of the class.

Model Detection: The same-sized model beneath "Train Model". It launches the *ModelDetectionGUI* class's run method and generates an instance of the class when clicked.

Figure: Main Menu Interface

2. Training Model(GUI)

The *GUI* class creates a window titled "SVM vs CNN-RNN" for selecting directories and models, and running the selected model. Components include:

Two entry fields with browse buttons for selecting directories for normal and attack data. A label displaying the current model (SVM or CNN-RNN). Two buttons for model selection. "Run Model" button to execute the selected model. Text area for log output. "Return" button to go back to the main menu.

create_entry_and_button: Creates an entry field and browse button, placing them in the window using the grid method and adding tooltips.

create_buttons: Creates the SVM, CNNRNN buttons and "Run Model" button.

create_status_label: Creates a label to display model execution status.

Figure: Train Model Interface

3. Model Detection (ModelDetectionGUI)

The *ModelDetectionGUI* class creates a window titled "Model Detection" for selecting a file and detecting it using SVM or CNN-RNN models. Components include:

Entry field with a browse button to select a file for detection. Two buttons to detect the file using SVM or CNN-RNN models. Text area to display detection results. "Return" button" to go back to the main menu.

browse_sample_file: Opens a file dialog box to browse for a file.

detect_data_by_SVM and detect_data_by_CNRRNN: Detect the file using the respective models and display the result.

Figure: Model Detection Interface

Result Analysis & Evaluation Criteria

The purpose of the research is to assess how well various models identify webshell attacks. Even though identifying webshell attacks is our main goal, our program can also identify all the attacks exists in the ADFA-LD dataset. We specifically examined the differences in performance between a Convolutional Neural Network - Recurrent Neural Network (CNN-RNN) model and a Support Vector Machine (SVM). The results of the evaluations are included here for precise understanding, with particular consideration given to each model's confusion matrix, starting time, recall, accuracy, and precision as well as its F1-score inside a classification report.

A. CNN-RNN Model

Training Time: The CNN-RNN model took 2.06 seconds to train.

CNN-RNN Model Performance Evaluation:

- (1) Accuracy: 0.9572784810126582
- (2) Precision: 0.9457627118644067
- (3) Recall: 0.9620689655172414
- (4) F1 Score: 0.9538461538461539
- (5) CNN-RNN Confusion Matrix:

[326	16]
[11	279]

Table Classification Report of CNN-RNN Model

Class	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Support
0 (Benign)	0.97	0.95	0.96	342
1 (Malicious)	0.95	0.96	0.95	290
Micro avg	0.96	0.96	0.96	632
Weighted avg	0.96	0.96	0.96	632

```

Train on 947 samples, validate on 632 samples
Epoch 1/15
947/947 [=====] - 6s 6ms/sample - loss: 0.6040 - accuracy: 0.6663 - val_loss: 0.4459 - val_accu
acy: 0.8165
Epoch 2/15
947/947 [=====] - 4s 4ms/sample - loss: 0.3872 - accuracy: 0.8342 - val_loss: 0.3116 - val_accu
acy: 0.8766
Epoch 3/15
947/947 [=====] - 4s 4ms/sample - loss: 0.2736 - accuracy: 0.8997 - val_loss: 0.3128 - val_accu
acy: 0.8892
Epoch 4/15
947/947 [=====] - 4s 4ms/sample - loss: 0.2360 - accuracy: 0.9187 - val_loss: 0.2388 - val_accu
acy: 0.9288
Epoch 5/15
947/947 [=====] - 4s 5ms/sample - loss: 0.1923 - accuracy: 0.9398 - val_loss: 0.2107 - val_accu
acy: 0.9383
Epoch 6/15
947/947 [=====] - 4s 5ms/sample - loss: 0.1600 - accuracy: 0.9409 - val_loss: 0.2052 - val_accu
acy: 0.9430
    
```

Figure: Epoch Details

Figure: Model Training and Validation Accuracy of CNN-RNN Model

The training and validation accuracy measures further validate the model's performance. As demonstrated in the Figures above, the training accuracy improves dramatically in the first epochs, reaching nearly 0.9 by the fourth epoch and continuing to rise, stabilizing around 0.95 state. The validation accuracy closely mirrored the training accuracy, eventually stabilizing between 0.9 and 0.95. These results show that the model can accurately categorize both normal and attack data.

Figure: Model Training and Validation Loss of CNN-RNN Model

The CNN-RNN model is trained for 15 epochs to improve its ability to recognize webshells. The above Figure: 'Epoch Details' and Figure: 'Model Training and Validation Loss of CNN-RNN Model' depicts the training and validation losses incurred throughout the process. The CNN-RNN model's loss curves demonstrate a reduction in training and validation loss over 15 epochs. The training loss decreased gradually from 0.6 to around 0.1, showing that the model was becoming more accurate. The validation loss also fell dramatically, stabilizing at approximately 0.2 after epoch 5. This shows that the model can generalize effectively to previously unseen data, which is critical for real-world applications. Although there is some uncertainty in the validation loss after the sixth epoch, it remains generally steady, indicating that the model is not significantly over fitted.

B. SVM Model

Training Time: The SVM model took 16.50 seconds to train.

SVM Model Performance Evaluation:

- (1) Accuracy: 0.9367088607594937
- (2) Precision: 0.9251700680272109
- (3) Recall: 0.9379310344827586
- (4) F1 Score: 0.9315068493150684
- (5) SVM Confusion Matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 320 & 22 \\ 18 & 272 \end{bmatrix}$$

Table: Classification Report of SVM Model

Class	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Support
0 (Benign)	0.95	0.94	0.94	342
1 (Malicious)	0.93	0.94	0.93	290
Micro avg	0.94	0.94	0.94	632
Weighted avg	0.94	0.94	0.94	632

C. Visualizing the Confusion Matrix

A confusion matrix is a table that evaluates the performance of a classification algorithm. The matrix uses target values to compare with predicted values. Each row in the matrix represents instances in a predicted class and each column represents instances in an actual class or vice versa. The matrix displays the number of instances produced by the model on the test data.-

Figure: Visual Representation of Confusion Matrix

The figure above represents the CNN-RNN model and SVM model's confusion matrix, which demonstrates its ability to classify normal and attack data. The CNN-RNN model identified correctly 326 normal samples (true positives) and 279 attack samples (true negatives). It however managed to provide 16 false positives (Type I Error), in which normal samples were misclassified as attack samples, and 11 false negatives (Type II Error), in which attack samples were mistaken for normal samples.

True Positive (TP): The CNN-RNN model predicted 326 samples as normal, which they are.

True Negative (TN): The model successfully identified 279 samples as attacks, and these are truly attack samples.

False Positive (FP): The model predicted 16 samples as normal, however they were really assault samples (Type I Error).

False Negative (FN): The model mistakenly predicted 11 samples as attacks when they were really normal samples (Type II error).

Similarly, the SVM model produced equivalent findings. The SVM model accurately detected 320 normal samples (True Positives) and 272 attack samples (True Negatives). However, it misidentified 22 normal samples as attacks (false positives) and 18 attack samples as normal (false negatives).

Table Calculation of Evaluation matrix

Model Name	Recall	Precision	Accuracy	F1 Score
SVM	0.94	0.93	0.9367	0.93
CNNRNN	0.96	0.95	0.95727	0.95

D. Comparative Analysis & Discussion

Table: Comparison of Evaluation Matrix

Model Name	Training Time	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Accuracy (ACC)	Micro avg	Weighted avg
CNNRNN	2.06	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.95727/0.96	0.96	0.96
SVM	16.50	0.93	0.94	0.93	0.9367/0.94	0.94	0.94

Table: Comparison of Confusion Matrix

Model Name	TP	FP	FN	TN
SVM	320	22	18	272
CNNRNN	326	16	11	279

As demonstrated in the Tables above, the performance comparison of the CNN-RNN and Support Vector Machine (SVM) models for webshell detection reveals several noteworthy findings. Significant enhancements in several important metrics were shown by the CNN-RNN model, highlighting its applicability in dynamic and real-time detection applications. The CNN-RNN model took significantly less time to train than the SVM model, requiring only 2.06 seconds instead of 16.50 seconds. This effectiveness is crucial for real-time applications where retraining or frequent model updates are desired. With a precision score of 0.95 as compared to 0.93 for the SVM model, the CNN-RNN model also demonstrated superior true positive identification and fewer false positives. Furthermore, with a recall score of 0.96, the CNN-RNN model outperformed the SVM model, which obtained a score of 0.94. This demonstrates how the CNN-RNN model can reduce false negatives while still successfully detecting real webshell attacks. Its 0.05 false positive rate, which is less than the SVM's 0.06 rate, further illustrates its capacity to cut down on false alarms.

Additionally, the CNN-RNN model showed a balanced performance in precision and recall, as well as reliability in categorizing both benign and malicious instances, with a higher F1 score of 0.957 and an accuracy of 0.96, respectively, than the SVM model's 0.9367 and 0.94. With the CNN-RNN model detecting 326 true positives and 279 true negatives, as opposed to the SVM model's 320 true positives and 272 true negatives, the confusion matrix analysis highlights these advantages. In addition, the CNN-RNN model significantly improved its accuracy in detecting webshell attacks by reducing false negatives to 11, which is a substantial improvement over the SVM model's 18 false negatives. These findings imply that the CNN-RNN model is especially well-suited for situations that require for precise, reliable, and fast webshell detection. In cases when high precision and recall are crucial and more lengthy training cycles are acceptable, the SVM model is still a good choice. The CNN-RNN model is ultimately the best option for improving web server security in real-time settings due to its exceptional performance across a variety of measurements.

Conclusion

In short up, the study successfully evaluated the efficacy of two models for webshell detection in system call sequences: Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Convolutional Neural Network-Recurrent Neural Network (CNN-RNN). Through an extensive comparison of performance parameters, such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and training length, the main goal was to evaluate their ability to identify malicious activity in system call traces. In addition to consuming a considerably shorter training time than the SVM model, the CNN-RNN model beat the SVM model, obtaining higher precision, recall, F1 score, and accuracy. These findings indicate that the CNN-RNN model's efficiency and higher recall rate make it especially beneficial for real-time intrusion detection systems. Despite its lengthy training time, the SVM model is still a good choice in situations when maximal recall and precision are crucial. The particular needs of the application, especially the trade-off between false positives and false negatives, should ultimately determine which of these models is appropriate.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Tang R, Yang Z, Li Z, et al. Zerowall: Detecting zero-day web attacks through encoder-decoder recurrent neural networks[C]//IEEE INFOCOM 2020-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications. IEEE, 2020: 2479-2488.
- [2] Mohammad N, Al-Hosni A, Al-Shaqsi A, Al-Mamari M, Al-Abri S. Web shell detection using naive Bayes classifier[J]. Journal of Information Security and Applications, 2014, 21: 55-63.
- [3] Zhang, Y., Zhang, Y., Zhang, Y., & Wang, Y. Web shell detection based on static and dynamic analysis[J] Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems, 2018, 35(5), 3509-3516.
- [4] Cover T, Hart P. Nearest neighbor pattern classification[J]. IEEE transactions on information theory, 1967, 13(1): 21-27.
- [5] Yuan L, Guo Y, Liu Y, Liu X. Deep learning-based webshell detection[C]. In: 2016 12th International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Security (CIS); 2016. pp. 299-303. IEEE.
- [6] Li X, He Z, Li X, Liu Z, Li W. A hybrid deep learning approach for webshell detection[J]. IEEE Access, 2021, 9: 23045-23053.
- [7] Wang, Y., Li, Y., & Li, M. A new method for webshell detection based on bidirectional GRU and attention mechanism[J]. Journal of Intelligent Information Systems, 2023 50(3), 715-731.
- [8] Zhang, Y., Li, Y., & Li, M. Webshell detection based on deep learning with transfer learning[J]. Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing, 2023, 14(5), 2865-2875.
- [9] Xie M, Hu J, Slay J. Evaluating host-based anomaly detection systems: Application of the one-class SVM algorithm to ADFA-LD[C]//2014 11th International Conference on Fuzzy Systems and Knowledge Discovery (FSKD). IEEE, 2014:

978-982.

- [10] Schuster M, Paliwal K. Bidirectional Recurrent Neural Networks[J]. IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing. 1997;45(11):2673-2681.
- [11] Hochreiter S, Schmidhuber J. Long Short-Term Memory[J]. Neural Computation. 1997; 9(8):1735-1780.
- [12] S. Sharma and S. Sharma, "Activation functions in neural networks" [J], Towards Data Science, vol. 6, no. 12, pp. 310–316, 2017.
- [13] B. Xu, N. Wang, T. Chen, and M. Li, "Empirical evaluation of rectified activations in convolutional network" [J], arXiv preprint arXiv:1505.00853, 2015.
- [14] Deshpande P, Sharma S C, Peddoju S K, Junaid S. Hids: A host based intrusion detection system for cloud computing environment[J]. International Journal of System Assurance Engineering and Management. 2018; 9(3):567-576.
- [15] Khandelwal P, Likhari P, Yadav R S. Machine learning methods leveraging ADFA-LD dataset for anomaly detection in linux host systems[C]//2022 2nd International Conference on Intelligent Technologies (CONIT). IEEE, 2022: 1-8.
- [16] Xie M, Hu J. Evaluating host-based anomaly detection systems: A preliminary analysis of adfa-ld[C]//2013 6th international congress on image and signal processing (CISP). IEEE, 2013, 3: 1711-1716.
- [17] Chawla A, Lee B, Fallon S, Jacob P. Host based Intrusion Detection System with Combined CNN/RNN Model[C]. In: ECML PKDD, Dublin; 2018.2018.
- [18] Creech G, Hu J. Generation of a new IDS test dataset: Time to retire the KDD collection[C]//2013 IEEE wireless communications and networking conference (WCNC). IEEE, 2013: 4487-4492.